

Turn-Blocking FTAs from the Perspective of Microaggression in the Trump-Zelenskyy Conference Meeting: A Forensic Linguistic Study

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates turn-blockings FTAs, known as non-cooperation acts, and the FTAs simultaneously performed alongside within the Trump–Zelenskyy conference meeting. Therefore, addressing how these FTAs function not merely as interactional disruptions, but as means for another FTA. The objectives are to identify the types of co-occurring FTAs and to analyse the tendency of how they are performed (degree of subtlety and intentionality based on a microaggression-informed perspective). Hence, adopting a descriptive qualitative methodology within a forensic linguistic approach and pragmatic analysis. Therefore, utilizes FTAs theory, supported by Speech Acts, while microaggression is merely used heuristically as a sensitizing perspective. As a result, while committing a non-cooperation acts, Trump predominantly performs indirect and subtle FTAs, such as irreverence, ridicule, contradiction, and others, which are realized through illocutionary acts that resemble microinvalidation-like and microinsult-like forms, indicating a high degree of intentionality. In contrast, Zelenskyy tends to perform more reactive and explicit FTAs, such as complains, criticism, challenge, and others, which approach microassault-like forms and reflect defensive counterattacks. The study demonstrates that non-cooperation acts purposed as gateways for broader FTAs in elite political discourse, and a forensic approach to microaggression is useful for identifying levels of subtlety and intentionality without going beyond the theoretical bounds of microaggression theory.

KEYWORDS: non-cooperation acts; face-threatening acts; forensic linguistic; microaggression perspective; Trump-Zelenskyy; conference meeting

I. INTRODUCTION

People are presumed to have polite, well-mannered talks with one another in order to convey their opinions, ideas, and beliefs in a socially diverse setting. From a linguistic perspective, this type of dialogue can be accomplished by observing to the rules of politeness that form the social norm and are thus generally recognized in contemporary culture. In practice, it can be easily compromised even though it might be readily relevant in particular situations. The majority of the time, a speaker will make strong and somewhat rude statements, usually out of urgency or anger, that result in an "attack" on the hearer. However, this usually leads to the hearer responding with a similar verbal "attack." These exchanges not only attack the mere individuals, but also their self-image or "face", as Goffman (1967) had defined it. This so-called "face attack" utterance is known as a face-threatening acts, or FTAs.

The face threatening-acts phenomenon occurs when a speaker ignores the interlocutor's self-image. This was conceptualized by Brown and Levinson (1987) who further categorize them into two major types according to face values, namely: negative face (individual's freedom of conduct) and positive face (individual's desire to be approved of). If one of these is ignored by the speaker during conversation, then an FTA is being performed towards the hearer. For example, in criticizing someone, the speaker disregards the hearer's positive face (to be approved of). Moreover, interrupting or refusing to let the hearer speak (turn-blocking) can be perceived as doing an FTA, or even multiple FTAs. The latter means the speaker, while doing so, continues to criticize them (adding another argument to his/her criticism). Nevertheless, it could happen the other way around, where a speaker is still in mid-sentence, and the interlocutor interrupts or prevents them from finishing (turn-blocking) by refuting and followed by criticizing them in return.

Since FTAs attempt to threaten and damage an individual's face, there is a possibility where they become verbal aggression. Nevertheless, verbal aggression itself can be varied, which ranged from blatant verbal violence to subtle verbal aggression in daily conversation. The latter is commonly known as Microaggression. Sue (2010) described it as a brief, subtle, and daily exchange that contains a diminutive message towards certain individuals. This type of verbal aggression is known for its subtlety and intentionality (can be intentional or unintentional). Regardless, this can threaten one's face, specifically individuals with certain

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marginalized backgrounds, which, according to Sue, can be: race, gender, or sexual orientation. But nowadays, it can be more than those three, such as mental health, ableism, religion, or even ideology. Therefore, it is likely to extend towards political views as well as political policies.

Through those backgrounds, the microaggression theories are central around power asymmetry and historical systemic inequality. Consequently, the impact of microaggression is mostly experienced by the individuals with such backgrounds, who tends to possess low structural power and have little to no ability to retaliate, hence making them marginalized and oppressed. In other words, microaggression is heavily tied to themes such as structural marginalization and asymmetrical social vulnerability. However, if it were applied to a high standing individual (for instance, a world leader), based on the strict theoretical and thematic sense, by no means could it be classified as microaggressions. Although heuristically speaking, it could happen. This is because the phenomenon can be similar, in a sense that the FTAs that may resemble microaggression forms within an interaction. To simply put it, both can be subtle and contain a degrading message, despite not having marginalized background. The subtlety may also link to the speaker's intentionality. According to Guillén-Nieto & Stein (2022, p. 1), those can be utilized as a perspective to offer evidence in observing the FTA phenomena, which is crucial in a Forensic Linguistics study, particularly involving people of high status, such as world leaders.

Discussions at bilateral meetings are expected to be polite and respectful of one another. All of this is due to the fact of the conversation they are having regards their future relation and the advancement of their respective nations. However, those expectations can be ignored in the face of a serious catastrophe, such as an impending war or even an ongoing one. A conference to reach agreements in such a situation may devolve into a series of arguments and even confrontations. Additionally, the speaker can utilize the hearer's political beliefs, policies, and ideologies (their social background) as a means to oppose the interlocutor's perspective. When this occurred, things can easily derail, from a formerly civilized discussion into a screaming match or hurling insults or even subtle ones. Furthermore, a speaker may opt to interrupt the hearer's replies or counterargument, which is known as a non-cooperation act. Nowadays, these have occurred and can be seen within a conference treaty between two conflicting parties, where each sides demand something in return. Nevertheless, this can also happen in another kind of meeting, such as a bilateral meeting, where one of the two is faced with a conflict and the other acts as a mediator.

This article is interested in investigating such a bilateral agreement, which was filled with a clash of views, beliefs, and policies towards the end of the conference. It involved a country's head of state that insisted on a peace diplomacy treaty as a solution to the conflict, and the other that had been through a lot of failed peace treaties in the past. Therefore, this study will observe and analyse the conference meeting between Trump (US) and Zelenskyy (Ukraine), the meeting which was expected to be filled with agreement but was filled with arguments and frequent interruption of each other member. Therefore, this study attempts to investigate the other kinds of face-threatening acts done, while doing a turn blocking, by specifically Trump and Zelenskyy as the speaker towards the hearer, and the way these FTAs can be viewed as microaggression-like forms.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Abellán (2024) conducted a corpus-based analysis on the North American presidential debate in order to investigate the face work phenomena. The literature examined the face work in a political discourse using theories as Benoit dan Wells' Face Restoration, Culpeper's Impoliteness Strategy, as well as Brown and Levinson's (1987) Face Threatening Acts. Consequently, the study identified the positive FTA tends to occur through impoliteness strategies, such as comparing the hearer (by finding disagreement, bringing up sensitive themes), and refusing to hear the hearer's objects, actions, and values. In reflection, it is relevant to this research because both examine FTAs. However, this research attempts to further investigate it from the perspective of microaggression, which the literature didn't do.

Holtgraves (2023) explored microaggression within context, which interrelated with pragmatics. The literature states that microaggression is a communicative act that can be classified as microinsults, microinvalidations, and indirect speech acts. Consequently, context played an important role in perceiving microaggression. Furthermore. the literature also highlights the importance to avoid misconception that intentionality is a requirement to utter a microaggression. This indicates that context, provided from speech acts (particularly illocution), can help determine a microaggression intentionality. Ultimately, this literature mainly discuss the interrelation of pragmatics (speech acts) dan microaggression, thereby making it relevant for this research to heuristically use microaggression as perspective to the FTA phenomenon, to which the literature hasn't attempted.

McCallaghan & Steyn (2025) investigated and deciphered the microaggression theory into a framework of theories, such as Critical Race Theory (CRT), Social Identity Theory (SID), and Social Domain Theory (SDT), in their review article. In other words, microaggressions involved a reliance on Critical Race Theory (CRT) to explain the ones revolving around race and racial forms of subtle discrimination. Meanwhile, it also highlights the marginal yet important roles of Social Identity Theory (SIT) and Social Domain Theory (SDT) as complementary lenses for non-racial ones. These findings may be relevant, specifically in using microaggression theory to further investigate the non-racial ones, i.e., related to politics. Unfortunately, the microaggression in this case is used as a perspective to view the linguistic phenomenon of FTA, which the literature hasn't provided.

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Cahyadi et. al. [5] examined the FTA, i.e., the kinds of FTAs and the strategies done by the speakers, from the political movie, “Darkest Hour”. This Qualitative study analysed the data based on Brown dan Levinson's (1987) theory, and found both negative and positive FTA towards the hearer (i.e., criticism, non-cooperation-act, reprimand, advice, request, etc.). Moreover, the speaker tends to do the FTAs directly, hence using the bald on record strategy. The literature is relevant since it utilizes Brown and Levinson’s theory as well. Nevertheless, it didn’t attempt to conduct further analysis based on the aspect of microaggression-like forms (utilizing the microaggression’s perspective).

Adi et. al. (2021) investigated the Face-Threatening Acts that occurred in the first 2020 US Presidential Debate. The qualitative study utilized Brown and Levinson’s theory to identify and categorize the respective FTAs uttered by Biden and Trump. As a result, Trump tends to perform Positive FTAs towards Biden (i.e., accusations), while Biden tends to perform FTAs towards himself (i.e., emotional leakage, such as uncontrollable laughter) as a response. Regardless of the common grounds and the relevance, this study is strictly focused on the FTA towards the hearer and attempts to find out the correlation of FTA with microaggression by using the latter’s perspective, which the literature hadn’t done.

In addition to the previous literature and studies, several theories are utilized as a framework to analyze and discuss the research problems at hand. Therefore, to further understand the face-threatening acts phenomenon, which is viewed from the microaggression perspective, this study utilized Brown and Levinson’s politeness theory, specifically on face threatening acts, as well as Sue’s microaggression for its theoretical framework. In addition, this study attempts to utilize Austin and Searle’s Speech Acts as a supporting theory.

III.METHODOLOGY

All The data of this study are in the form of an utterance, transcribed from Trump-Zelenskyy Conference meeting video back on February 28th, 2025, which was acquired from the C-SPAN YouTube Channel. Furthermore, this research is conducted with a Descriptive Qualitative Methodology along with a Forensic Linguistic theoretical Approach, which was achieved by utilizing the microaggression theory as a perspective to view the non-cooperation FTA, which, heuristically speaking, can be similar to the microaggression phenomenon. In other words, it did not involve classifying the data as microaggressions in the strict theoretical sense, but drawing heuristic categories based on the microassault, microinsult, and microinvalidation to describe the formal interactional similarities. Consequently, these categories are not treated as socio-structural acknowledgements but as mere perspective (descriptive lenses) that helps to differentiate degrees of subtlety (indirectness), deniability/intentionality, and FTA within the object of this study. The microaggressions perspective, thereby, meant to sensitize the forensic-pragmatic analysis that leans to subtle, deniable forms of harmful language use and delegitimization, which are central concerns in forensic linguistics.

Furthermore, to understand the FTA and Microaggression phenomenon, specifically occurred within the Bilateral Conference meeting between Trump and Zelenskyy, this study proposed a Thematic Analysis, which includes steps, such as gathering and familiarizing the utterance, creating codes (i.e., speech acts, specific FTA), defining the themes based on that code (i.e., FTAs that occurred besides Non-cooperation acts, intentionality of the utterance), reviewing and defining the themes (specific FTA that may threatens the hearer’s positive/negative face, and the microaggression-like phenomenon), then finally write the analysis in a descriptive paragraph. Moreover, this study utilized an instrument, namely ELAN, to help discover the non-cooperation FTAs, as well as to further untangle the utterance and discussion between the interlocutors. In addition, the result also includes the table of corresponding speakers, the classification of other FTAs, and their microaggression perspective (microaggression-like forms).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are plenty cases of non-cooperation acts were found and had occurred throughout the meetings. Most of them have the same types of co-occurring FTAs and microaggression-like forms. Among them, one type would be selected to represent their co-occurrence FTAs and their microaggression-like form. There are FTAs, includes **complains, criticism, irreverence, and challenge**, that resemble the **microassault-like form**. There are also FTAs that includes (another) **irreverence, ridicule, and insult**, which appear similar to **microinsult-like in form**. In addition, FTAs such as **disapproval, contradiction, reprimand, and disagreement**, which perceived to be akin to a **microinvalidation-like form**. Furthermore, an example of each microaggression-like form and their respective co-occurring FTAs is available on Table 1 below. Furthermore, the discussion on the respective other kinds of FTA (that co-occurred) and their form based on the microaggression perspective will be discussed consecutively for each utterance.

Table 1. Example of each microaggression-like FTAs (microaggression perspective) and their co-occurring FTAs

<i>Microaggression Perspective</i>	<i>Simultaneous FTAs (co-occurred with Non-cooperation Acts)</i>	<i>Speaker</i>	<i>Utterances</i>
Microassault-like	Criticism	Zelenskyy	<i>You invited me here. You invited me</i>

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			<i>here to speak.</i>
Microinsult-like	Contempt or Ridicule	Trump	<i>You're not winning. You're not winning this.</i>
Microinvalidation-like	Contradiction	Trump	<i>You- You haven't been alone. You haven't been alone.</i>

A. Non-Cooperation FTAs Resembling Microassault-like Form

These non-cooperation acts can be considered resembling a microinvalidation due to the nature of their subtlety and their context. This involves attacking the hearer's ideals or knowledge/background on purpose or intentional. This, of course, is with the exception of that systemic oppression feature that involves in an actual microassault. Thereby making these a microassault-like FTAs. As a result, these are the comprised of **complains** (i.e., (46:28) *It doesn't matter for you what the ceasefire means*), **irreverence** (i.e., (44:27) *Oh what? What are you speaking about?*), **criticism** (i.e., (45:14) *You invited me here. You invited me here to speak.*), and **challenge** (i.e., (43:43) *From the very, from the very beginning of the war, from the very beginning of the war Mr. President, I-*), which can be found in the Trump-Zelenskyy meeting.

1. Complains

The first utterance is uttered towards Trump claiming that he does not care about the outcome of his peace treaty. This implies that, according to Zelenskyy, Trump only wants to push his own agenda (in becoming the mediator of two conflicting countries) without actually knowing the background of the previous failed peace agreements. The background involves one of the member states wanting security guarantees in order to prevent further failure. However, the US president disregard it, as he assumed the guarantees can be a provocation for the other member thus making the agreement failed instead. Nevertheless, the utterance has an implication of expressing the speaker's annoyance towards Trump, thus indicating the presence of expressive illocutionary.

Through those argument and debates, Zelenskyy utter a statement that expresses his dissatisfaction towards Trump's standing. This implies that he wants Trump to stop insisting on his grand plan and listen to his plea concerning the guarantees of security in order to prolong and support the ceasefire attempt through this peace talks. Consequently, this represents Zelenskyy's negative evaluation towards Trump and his persistence with the idea that his peace talk can occur smoothly without involving any security guarantee details. Therefore, while interrupting Trump, Zelenskyy performed a **complain** that threatens both Trump's positive face (to be liked or approved of).

This complains, driven by the expressive illocutionary, subtly hints his dissatisfaction towards Trump peace plan. This is driven by his own persistence and assumption that all of that will fail (just as the previous ones did) without a detailed security guarantees Nevertheless, This FTA implies that he does not approve of and willing to partake in Trump's mediation with Russia. As a result, this subtle complains purposely attack Trump's arguments. This can be similar with a microassault form, thus making it a **microassault-like FTA**.

2. Irreverence

The second utterance (*Oh what? What are you speaking about?*) also belongs to Zelenskyy. He uttered it against Vance who accused him of campaigning for the opposition in October and followed by ordering him to say his gratitude (towards Trump). This response is in a form of a question that ask the interlocutor to specify what he meant. However, it does not attempt to do so. As a matter of fact, the question itself implies that the speaker has no knowledge of what the interlocutor is saying. It means the Ukrainian president purposely disacknowledges the claims and order stated by Vance. Therefore, the question is rhetorical and driven by an illocutionary act, specifically an expressive illocutionary.

By saying a rhetorical question, the president of Ukraine implicitly expresses his disinterest of Vance's statement (his FTAs). This can also be seen as a means to say that the interlocutor has the wrong idea. Moreover, he uttered it while interrupting the FTAs hurled by Vance (i.e., accusation and order). This indicates that Zelenskyy utilized his utterance as a defence against those FTAs and attacking Vance in return. Nevertheless, this specific FTAs carries the speaker's negative evaluation towards Vance and does so by not showing his attention and respect. As a result, this non-cooperation act simultaneously commits an **irreverence** that threatens the hearer's positive face twice.

Based on the disrespectful and irreverence intention, Zelenskyy wish to silence his interlocutor. He specifically wants his interlocutor to stop his accusation, of which he perceived as false. Consequently, by saying such utterance, Zelenskyy subtly built an assumption that the US vice president is wrong. Thereby, intentionally attacking the accusation's credibility, an in extension, the interlocutor's credibility. Due to those factors, this subtle act of irreverence can be seen akin to a microaggression, specifically a **microassault-like FTAs**.

3. Criticism

The third utterance was a response to Trump constant attack that appears to belittling him of his current situation. In other words, this utterance is sparked by Trump's statement (FTAs) that Ukraine would only and up until then, stood a chance, because of the US military equipment. Thereby implying that Zelenskyy should cease his debate and insisting upon security guarantees for

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the peace agreements mediated by the US. In accordance to that, Zelenskyy responds with a statement claiming that his purpose in the meeting is, in fact, to give feedback upon the peace talks based on his past experience dealing with the conflict. Due to that, the statement is driven by an illocutionary act,

Zelenskyy refutes with a statement asserting his role as the member state that would be most afflicted and impacted by the agreements. This rebuttal asserts his position to defy and rectify Trump's mistake and misconception of the conflict, i.e., that it cannot be subdued by mere diplomacy but only through a diplomatic peace talk involving detailed security guarantees for the conflicting parties. This is what Zelenskyy attempts to imply while stating his assertive FTA regarding his role in the conference meeting. Subsequently, it indicates his dismissal towards Trump's FTAs, and in extension, his misconceptions and deeming them as something negative. Therefore, this turn-blocking FTA also acts as a **Criticism** that threatens Trump's positive face.

This assertive criticism towards Trump is meant specifically to counterattack his FTAs. However, this may also attack the US president's ideals and principal, which he held tightly. These ideals are related to how Trump would envision the peace be (without the need of security guarantees). Subsequently, Zelenskyy tried to rectify those perceptions by intentionally proclaiming and asserting his role. The Ukrainian president hoped to subtly make Trump realize of his errors, and finally, to be allowed to speak further regarding the betterment of the future treaty based on his past experience. In accordance to that, the criticism FTA relates to a **microassault-like FTAs** due to its nature of intentionality and purposed subtlety.

4. Challenge

By uttering this statement, Zelenskyy attempts to reject and refute the FTAs imposed by Trump towards him. This imposition by Trump is mainly criticizing that Ukraine is on a bad position because of the president's own fault. To put it simply, the US president implicitly held a contempt towards the speaker, and due to that, he uttered an argument to paint his strength and perseverance from the very beginning. This unfortunately would be interrupted by Trump later. Nevertheless Zelenskyy, through the statement, attempts to rectify Trump's understanding and perception of him and his country. In order to do so, the statement would involve an assertive illocutionary act.

Through this assertive utterance, the Ukrainian president tries to prove that Trump is wrong about him and his country being in a not very good position. This is done by implying that they are staying strong and remain persevere throughout the conflict until the moment of the conference meeting. Subsequently, the utterance implicitly delivers a disapproval towards Trump's judgement and in return, gives a negative evaluation towards him. This is done by performing a non-cooperating act that **challenges** the interlocutor at the same time. Thus, threatening the US president positive face in a fold.

Furthermore, this face threatening act of challenge, attempt indicates Zelenskyy's disapproval of Trump's ranting and defamation of his presidency and his country. This utterance serves as a subtle means to indicate that the interlocutor (as well as his statement) is very wrong. In other words, the subtle yet direct defiance suggests that the situation is not the same as the ones being framed by the US president. This intentional FTA (which signifies the perseverance of Ukraine), ultimately, attacks Trump's credibility to paint the actual situation or crisis that Ukraine currently facing. Moreover, the aftermath of such attack can be seen by the general public. Therefore, the challenge resembles a form of microaggression, i.e., a **microassault-like FTAs**.

B. Non-Cooperation FTAs Resembling Microinsult-like Form

These non-cooperation acts can be considered resembling a microinsult due to the nature of their subtlety and their context (of demeaning the hearer). This, of course, is with the exception of that systemic oppression feature that involves in an actual microinvalidation. Therefore, making them a microinsult-like FTAs. As a result, these are the comprised of **irreverence** (i.e., (43:40) *You're right now not in a very good position.*), **ridicule** (i.e., (44:47) *You're not winning. You're not winning this.*), and **brings bad news towards the hearer and boasting himself** (i.e., (45:13) *If you didn't have our military equipment, this war would have been over in two weeks*), which can be found in the Trump-Zelenskyy meeting.

1. Irreverence

This specific statement was uttered by Trump in the midst of debating Zelenskyy, whom insisted on having security guarantees and without them they would feel the impact of ongoing conflict. Subsequently, the speaker implies the unnecessary of such things since they would more likely provoke Russia to not having a peace talk mediated by him. The series of arguments filled with Trump mentioning Zelenskyy's current position, which he's in need of help urgently, so there's no place of making demands. Ultimately, he uttered the non-cooperation act which was driven by a declarative illocutionary act of declaring the gravity of the hearer's situation.

Through an interruptive declaration, Trump aims to stop Zelenskyy's persistence on wanting and demanding a detailed security guarantee, of which he deemed unnecessary. He implies that it would sabotage the agreement they're trying to achieve, which is crucial considering Ukraine current situation. In other words, the speaker wanted Zelenskyy to stop dictating (through his negative prediction of not having security guarantee) and allow the US to carry out the peace talks in order to help him achieve a better position. Ultimately, this hints a negative evaluation towards Zelenskyy's attitude and desire, thus performing an **irreverence** while doing the non-cooperation act, which both threatens his positive face.

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Furthermore, this act of irreverence, which involved turn blocking and negative declaration, suggests that the speaker does not wish to fulfil the hearer's desire. As a matter of fact, he tried to divert such topics by mentioning the current position of the Ukrainian's president is in. This subtly belittles his effort to gain a security guarantee and urges him to believe in Trump's plan. It is worth mentioned that prior to this declaration, Trump made a promise of how his agreement would be for the betterment of his speaker. Therefore, he purposely mentioned his irreverence utterance to paint a contrast, to urge the hearer. With this, the FTA may resemble a form of microaggression, which is a **microinsult-like FTA**.

2. Ridicule

In the similar context to his previous irreverence, Trump still found Zelenskyy persistently clinging to his ideals, even continued to argue with him and his vice president. This sparks another statement, similar to the previous one yet has more clarity. This involved him saying that Zelenskyy is currently losing a war. This reflects Trump's effort to battle his hearer's persistence by declaring a negative fact about him. This means that it involves a similar declarative illocutionary.

Trump, once again, declaring a negative situation which Zelenskyy's facing. However, this one has more clarity to its message. Nevertheless, he did this as an effort to dismantle Zelenskyy's belief and urge him to just accept his peace talks without further arguing. Implicitly, this means that Trump still harbour his negative evaluation towards Zelenskyy and refuse to let him continue his arguments. As a result, Trump simultaneously ridicules his hearer while doing this non-cooperation act, and thus threatening Zelenskyy's positive face in a fold.

Moreover, Trump's seemed to refuse to let others including Zelenskyy, who will be actively impacted, to meddle with the peace talks that he had envisioned. He perceives this as an act of compromise and sabotage. This is the reason why he actively tried to subtly avoid a criticism which can be demonstrated by the current turn blocking and ridicule. In accordance to that, this means that he consciously and purposely performed those FTAs. Thus, making it resemble to a form of microaggression, specifically a **microinsult-like FTA**.

3. Bringing bad news about the Hearer and Boasting Self

As a continuation to the previous ridicule, the situation becomes even more heated, since Zelenskyy rebuts with the fact that they are staying strong and that they have been alone. Subsequently, Trump challenge such statement claiming that the US have been helping them throughout the years, providing funds and military equipment. The US president's argument is closed with yet another negative and even more demeaning statement regarding the probability of the war without US's intervention. This proves that the speaker is asserting a claim that regards him and the US, hence proving an occurrence of an assertive illocutionary.

This assertive demeaning message states that Ukraine would have lost the war in two weeks' time without the help and involvement of the US, specifically the military equipment. Through this degrading statement, Trump urges Zelenskyy to stop arguing by reminding him that he's in need of the US help, thereby belittling the effort Ukrainian forces and mocking its president's desire, implicitly. In addition, this negative message adds another layer of intimidation since Trump highlighted the urgent dependence and reliance of Ukraine towards US, and may be more in the future (through Trump's peace negotiation). As a result, the speaker, through this non-cooperation act, simultaneously **brings bad news towards the hearer and boasting himself**, thus threatening the hearer's positive face twice.

Moreover, the US President attempted to remind the Ukrainian president, who appears to have owed him, in order to obey him. So, not He utilizes this to close his refute on the claims (that Ukraine has been alone) but also to urge him to accept his peace agreement that he had envision with open arms and without complain. In addition, this statement also subtly hints that the help could be revoke at any time. This would put Ukraine in an even tougher spot and thus adding another layer of bad news. Nevertheless, this form of intimidation uses an intentional demeaning message, thereby resembles to a form of microaggression and making it a microinsult-like FTA

C. Non-Cooperation FTAs Resembling Microinvalidation-like Form

These non-cooperation acts can be considered resembling a microinvalidation due to the nature of their subtlety and their context (of dismissing the hearer's thoughts and deeming them irrelevant). This, of course, is with the exception of that systemic oppression feature that involves in an actual microinvalidation. Thereby making these a microinvalidation-like FTAs. Therefore, FTAs such as disapproval (i.e., (37:48) *They'll be protected. The agreement will protect them*), **reprimand** (i.e., (44:11) *That's back to you. Far more than a lot of people said they should have*), **contradict** (i.e., (45:00) *You- You haven't been alone. You haven't been alone*), **disagreement** (i.e., *Of course, Of course, we want to stop the war. But I said-*), were found belonging to the microinvalidation-like form in the Trump-Zelenskyy conference meeting.

1. Disapproval

This statement was an answer attempt by Trump to a CNN reporter asking him the protector of Ukraine after the agreement. However, the answer can be perceived as a bit vague. This is due to the fact that he claimed the agreement itself with protect them instead of specifying a concrete form of protection based on that agreement. This indicates the speaker's wish to dismiss the reporter. This means the utterance contains an illocutionary act, namely an assertive illocutionary

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This form of vague statement attempts to assert a claim that the topic is not to be discussed further and should be dismissed. This subtle rejection implies Trump's disinterest in continuing to discuss the topic. This is because the topic of protection would involve a security guarantee, which he refused to explain further (based on his own assumption that it would sabotage the agreement). Regardless, this indicates Trump's negative evaluation towards the question and the reporter herself. Therefore, while interrupting the hearer's speech, Trump uttered a subtle **disapproval** that goes against her desires and threatens her positive face.

The disapproval implied that Trump wish to discuss other matter. Due to that he rejected the reporter's question by giving a vague answer instead. Furthermore, this rejection can also indicate that the reporter is perceived by Trump as not in a capacity/clearance to know a detailed information regarding his agreement. Based on that, the FTA can be akin to a form of microaggression, specifically the microinvalidation-like.

2. Reprimand

This utterance was a response toward Zelenskyy at the end of his arguments regarding the position of Ukraine in the agreement. This is proceeding the speaker's microinsult-like irreverence. This utterance states that the Ukrainian president is overstepping his position by stating more that he should have, and at the same time, attempts to influence the peace talk arrangement to suit his experience. The statement involves an expressive illocutionary in order to convey the expression of disappointment.

This statement involves Trump rebuking Zelenskyy's behaviour throughout the meeting (up until that point). The US president was displeased by how the Ukrainian president act as his guest, i.e. debating him and demanding security guarantees that can be perceived as entitlement and overstepping the host. Therefore, he interrupts the hearer's plea and delivers his negative evaluation towards him. In other words, Trump utters a reprimand towards Zelenskyy by doing a non-cooperation act, which simultaneously threaten the hearer's positive face in a fold.

In addition, the reprimand suggests Trump's condemnation of such behaviour that the Ukrainian president demonstrate. Implicitly, he tried to silence his hearer's persistence and arguments that were attacking him. Subsequently, the speaker might perceive the hearer's thought as a hinderance (towards his masterplan of achieving peace for the sake of the hearer's country), and gives him the rights to dismiss them. To a certain degree, this would resemble a microaggression, specifically a **microinvalidation-like** form.

3. Contradiction

This utterance was uttered by Trump towards Zelenskyy as a response to the hearer's claim that Ukraine has been alone from the beginning of the conflict. It is specifically uttered prior to the microinsult-like FTA regarding the military equipment. Moreover, this suggest that Trump blatantly reject the claim and uttered a counter statement and repeats them. Consequently, the utterance is influenced by a declarative illocutionary, proclaiming the opposite of what the hearer said.

With this declarative statement, Trump refuse to acknowledge Zelenskyy's claim. This is because the United State, even before Trump's presidency, has send many fundings and military aids to Ukraine. Moreover, the US president perceive Zelenskyy's overstatement (of Ukraine's struggle) as an attempt of spreading misinformation that would lead to a defamation towards his country, which is why he urgently state the opposite. Consequently, this represents his negative evaluation towards Zelenskyy and his statement. Therefore, he commits an interruption containing a **contradiction** towards the hearer, which ultimately threatens his positive face.

With this contradictory statement, Trump subconsciously deny the legitimacy of the claim and subtly paints Zelenskyy as an unreliable narrator. But at the same time, he would decline the legitimacy of Ukraine's hardship, where in a certain time they were alone in the battlefield against Russia. This would dismiss the genuine struggle and effort done by Ukraine and overshadow them with the help from the US, (which the speaker later points out and takes credits from). Subsequently, this is akin to a form of microaggression, which would be a microinvalidation-like FTA.

4. Disagreement

This was uttered by Zelenskyy as a rebuttal to Trump's accusation beforehand. He was accused wanting to prolong the war just because he wants a security guarantee and claims that the past agreements fail to maintain ceasefire. Specifically, he wants to tell Trump to have the ceasefire with security guarantee in order to prepare for the worst-case scenario. Subsequently, the utterance would involve an expressive illocutionary to express a difference of opinion.

Through this statement Zelenskyy insisted that he wants to stop the war only if he achieved it once and for all. Because of that, he thinks a detailed security guarantee is important. In accordance to that, he implicitly wants Trump to add a detailed them in his peace talks that he had envision. The Ukrainian president deemed it necessary in order to keep the ceasefire from being breeched (especially by Russia). Therefore, he uttered a **disagreement** by interrupting trumps accusation, which ultimately threatens the hearer's positive face.

Furthermore, this statement explicitly delivers the speaker's intention to demand and have a security guarantee through the peace negotiation mediated by the US. This would go against Trump's desire and in addition to that, implicitly evaluating Trump's capability in creating a lasting peace without a security guarantee. As a result, this subtle implication would resemble a form of microaggression that dismisses the hearer's background. Thereby, making this statement a **microinvalidation-like** FTA.

Non-Cooperation Acts from the Perspective of Microaggression in the Trump-Zelenskyy Conference Meeting

CONCLUSIONS

This study managed to discover the turn blocking FTAs (or a non-cooperation act) is in fact can occur simultaneously, specifically in the Trump–Zelenskyy conference meeting. By adopting a forensic linguistic approach and interpreting the findings through a microaggression perspective, the analysis demonstrates that non-cooperation FTA often co-occur. These acts can be comprised of **complains, criticism, challenge, irreverence, ridicule, brings bad news towards the hearer and boasting himself, disapproval, reprimand, contradiction, and disagreement**. Therefore, proving the non-cooperation acts can systematically functioned as a means for these FTAs that are varied in type, subtlety, and intentionality, which depend on the interlocutors, i.e., Trump and Zelenskyy.

Moreover, the analysis found the subtlety and intentionality of the simultaneous FTAs are not evenly distributed. Subsequently, The US president tends to perform FTAs resembling to microinvalidation (microinvalidation-like FTAs) and microinsult (microinsult-like FTAs) forms, while the Ukrainian president tends to perform them with something akin to microassault (microassault-like FTAs). The subtle and deniable FTAs (microinvalidation-like and microinsult-like form) suggest the characteristic of the speaker occupying a higher institutional position, while more explicit and confrontational FTAs (microassault-like forms, which are not so subtle and intentional) are uttered from the interlocutor responding to the former. This supports the argument that, although the interaction cannot be classified as microaggression in the strict theoretical sense (due to the absence of structural marginalization and systemic oppression), microaggression perspective provides a valuable interpretive lens for distinguishing degrees of indirectness (subtlety), deniability, and strategic intent in such an elite political discourse.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that turn blocking FTAs (non-cooperation acts) in elite diplomatic interaction function not merely as interruptions, but as interactional gateways for broader face-threatening strategies. When viewed through a microaggression informed forensic-pragmatic perspective, these strategies reveal how subtle linguistic choices can serve as tools of power negotiation, delegitimizing, and resistance between interlocutors of high standing. Future research may extend this approach to other elite political encounters to further explore how micro-level linguistic hostility operates beyond contexts of structural oppression and marginalization.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Author expresses gratitude to the supervisors who gave guidance, wisdom, and encouragement, and also accompanied the author towards the completion of this article as part of the master's thesis.

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